

Impacts of Overfishing on the Marine Ecosystem

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Abstract

The global fish and fishing industries are expanding quickly because fish is an essential source of protein. The seafood business is very profitable for many nations. It is giving many individuals both work prospects and a significant economic boost. New techniques have emerged in response to growing demand. Concern grows as its demand spreads throughout the globe. Due to its high demand and rising cost, overfishing has increased. Changing catches alone won't solve the problem; there is a need to work on sustainable fishing. Fish populations in seas and oceans are dwindling due to climate change and global warming. When temperature changes and ocean warming exceed an organism's ideal range, physiological reactions are triggered, which then influence biological responses. Reviewing some of the literature will help readers understand why fish populations are dropping and what may be done to stop it.

Keywords: Marine Ecosystem, Overfishing, Aquaculture survey

1. Introduction

The fishing business is expanding quickly in the modern era and supports the economies of many coastal developing nations. Given its size, the fishing industry generates a huge number of jobs. It benefits the economy by lowering the unemployment rate, which is a growing problem. The fishing sector also generates significant profits for China, Japan, and the United States. This lucrative industry causes overfishing. Simply said, overfishing occurs when there are too many fish being taken from the ocean at rapid rates

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for the breeding population to have enough to reproduce and increase in size. Overfishing first occurred in the 1800s when people soaked bubbles for lamp oil. Following that, three further firms and the Arctic Alaska fishing companies were introduced by Tycoon in the 19th century. They run a fleet of heavy industrial trawlers. 400 tons of fish are caught at single netting by these trawlers as they pull nylon net through the water. International initiatives made in the early 20th century to promote the accessibility and affordability of protein-rich foods resulted in concerted government action. Overfishing results from attempts to improve fishing capacity and catch fish once more. The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture surveys claim that (SOFIA). The Mediterranean and Black seas are the most overfished in the world, with 62% of their fish stock currently overfished and in grave danger of extinction. Quartz India cites certain Indian companies that used to purchase both trash fish and by catch in addition to fresh fish. Initially, fishermen just caught fish, but today, they are encouraged to also catch other marine species, which causes the loss of both fish and marine animals. Previously, only a small fraction of the catch was wasted, and that piece was donated to various companies, but now, in an effort to increase their income, fishermen are catching everything in the sea. 1414 species of fish, or 5% of all known species worldwide, are on the International Union for Conservation of Nature's (IUCN) Red List of Endangered Species. Because identifying endangered species can be challenging. Some of the endangered species, according to reports, are:

1.1 Blue fin Tuna (*Thunnus thynnus*)

The North Atlantic Ocean is where you may mostly find blue fin tuna (Fig. 1). Blue fin tuna are severely overfished since they are highly sought-after and pricey (\$100,000 per fish). It has been determined that blue fin tuna is the sixth-most endangered species on land, at sea (WWF).

Figure.1 Entangled Blue fin in Fishing Net (Courtesy: www.dfo-mpo.qc.ca)

1.2 Bigeye Tuna (*Thunnusobesus*)

Bigeye tuna is great for cutlets, grilling, barbecuing, baking, and smoking because it has thick fillets with a flavour that is reminiscent of flesh. Fish most popular in Japan Bigeye Tuna is overfished for sushi and sashimi, as well as for frozen and fresh in other markets, as sushi and sashimi have highlighted some species' exceptional eating characteristics raw (WWF). They are transported early in the morning to the auction (Fig .2) According to the International Sea Food Sustainability Foundation, the Eastern and Western Pacific Oceans see the most overfishing of bigeye tuna.

Figure.2 Bigeye Tuna being carried to Auction. (Courtesy: pnewswire.com)

1.3 Albacore Tuna (*Thunnusalalunga*)

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Figure.3 Albacore Tuna Hanging for Sale (Courtesy: ypte.org.uk)

The smallest species of tuna in the family is the albacore. Long pectoral fins are present (Fig.3). They move through the Mediterranean and all ocean waters in single-species schools (WWF, 2012). Since tuna is mostly caught for commercial purposes, it gives people access to food (in the form of canned goods) and a means of subsistence. In addition, because tuna is one of the top predators in the marine food chain, it contributes to the preservation of the ocean's ecosystem. The albacore tuna supply is severely overfished, and the biomass is at historically low levels, according to a 2015 report by the International Seafood Sustainability Foundation. Albacore stocks in the northern and southern Atlantic Oceans are overfished (IISF). Although there have been numerous movements around the world to boycott the production, eating, and serving of this fish in restaurants, people's taste buds just can't resist this one of the world's most delectable fishes (Fig.4)

1.4 Maltese Ray (*Leucorajamelitensis*)

The Mediterranean Sea, along the coasts of Italy, Algeria, Malta, and Tunisia, is where you can mostly find Maltese Rays. This fish is reportedly in danger of extinction due to habitat loss. Maltese rays have a modest growth rate, a late sexual maturity, and only a small number of offspring. Maltese rays are rarely taken by commercial fishing; instead, they are sometimes grabbed as by catch by boats harvesting other species (Fig. 4) and then tossed back into the water dead or dying since they were unwanted. The regional government made no significant efforts to protect this Maltese ray.

Figure.4 Maltese Ray Fish Accidentally Caught (Courtesy: en.m.wikipedia.org)

1.5 Goliath Grouper (*Epinephelus itajara*)

Another name for Goliath Grouper is Jewfish. It is primarily found in the subtropical regions of the Atlantic and Eastern Pacific from Baja California to Peru (from North Carolina to Brazil). It is a huge fish (Fig. 5), measuring 7 feet long and having a lifespan of 40 years (WWF, 2012). Goliath generates very few progeny since they are in the

reproductive stage for such a brief time. They are primarily taken in by catch, which is why their population is steadily declining.

Figure.5 South Carolina Fishermen Catch a 400-Pound Goliath Grouper (Courtesy: alamy stock photos)

1.6 European Eel (*Anguilla Anguilla*)

These can be found in the Baltic, Mediterranean, and North Atlantic waters. They have an extremely unusual life cycle that begins with birth in the ocean and continues in freshwater streams thousands of kilometres inland, where they grow to a length of 4.5. Between the ages of 6 and 30, when they achieve sexual maturity, they return to the water to spawn. Every year, millions of eels die during their normal migration (Fig.6). Most of Europe's 25,000 hydroelectric power facilities and many tens of thousands of pumping stations are not properly inspected. Numerous of them are badly constructed, making it impossible for fish to go around or through them. Species that migrate over great distances, like the European eel, are severely reduced or perhaps on the verge of extinction.

Figure.6 European eels Killed in their Native Environment (Courtesy: alamy stock photos)

1.7 Winter Skate (*Leucaenaocellate*)

In the northwest Atlantic Ocean, from Canada's Gulf of St. Lawrence to North Carolina in the United States, are winter skates. This fish species is remarkable in that it shocks its prey to protect itself (WWF) Winter skaters are the most often taken of these species for human consumption (Fig. 7), as their wing meat. Winter skates develop slowly, take a while to mature, and live a long time if not killed. Due to overfishing, this fish population is steadily diminishing (ESS).

Figure.7 Winter Skates used to Make Meat (Courtesy: alamy stock photos)

1.8 Currently, Fishes' Conditions

Today's greatest threat to the marine ecology is seen to be growing overfishing. Everything has a limit, and if we use something to its full potential, it will suffer. Because marine life continues to be a key source of food for humans, fish stocks are overfished and declining. Fishing has been done by humans for a very long time utilising lines, hooks, and boats. Until the middle of the 19th century, fishing methods were sustainable. The mid-20th century saw a rapid change in fishing methods, as well as increased government initiatives to improve fishing capacity, which led to new fishing techniques and the quick growth of big industrial scale enterprises. Because fishing hooks catch a lot of fish and are not selective, many non-target species are also destroyed (FAO 1999, Hilborn et al. 2003) An estimated 38 million people work as fisherman or fish growers worldwide (FAO,2009). There are urgent requests for strict management and the creation of protected areas as a result of the fact that many fish stocks and species have today fallen since their historical peaks and some have already collapsed. (Roberts and others 2003)

2. Literature Review

This literature exploration focal point is largely on the point of “Overfishing” and the situation of fishes across the world. Most of the fish we commonly eat will no longer exist (Kurlansky).

Martecoll et al. [9] describe the Due to the elimination of prey, overfishing can result in the depletion of secondary production at higher trophic levels, which is the generation of mass and energy by all consumers in the ecosystem, including both herbivores and carnivores. The overfishing has significantly escalated from 1950 to the 2000s.

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Figure.8 Ecosystem Overfishing in the Ocean (Courtesy: plos.org)

Figure.9 Average status of major fisheries (Courtesy: ioelondonblog.wordpress.com)

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Ray Hilborn et al. [4] states that the total world catch from oceans was declining that's how we came to know about the extinction of fishes. The fishing industry is a thriving business that supports several countries' economies, and a main source of income, and this encourages overfishing. In most of the countries where we can see a decline of fishes there is a race for fish in which everyone is competing from each other to get more fish before anyone else. Fish being caught not allowing for the smaller infertile fish rich sexual maturity to reproduce and continue the population growth.

Paul J. Radomski [12] describes that population growth; international market demands and arrival of illegal fishers have declined the number of fish species. Not only the numbers are declining but also some fish species are in the list of endangered and extinct. Sustainable management of fisheries are required but failure of sustainable management of fisheries has uncompromising ecological, economical, and social cost. Corporate business professionals can might get profit by throwing industrial waste in seas and oceans and polluting them. Just as Commercial fishers can get profit by overfishing. Commercial fishers only think about money they don't care about the extinction of fishes as we can see that in Fig. 10 that the workers are processing fish at the plant of the Red Lake Band.

Figure.10 Workers processing fish at the plant of the Red Lake Band of Chippewa Indians, Red Lake, Minnesota (Courtesy: alamy.com)

3. Methodology

The report begins with a thorough introduction to the research that I conducted, in which I attempted to explain overfishing and its effects. Due to COVID, it was not appropriate to go outdoors and collect data in the field, so the strategy utilised to finish this paper was a secondary approach, which involved using the data that was already available. When it comes to my research paper's sources, I looked at a variety of books, magazines, newspapers, and websites. The research papers selected for this journal article focused

primarily on the subject. A crucial procedure that includes data collection, analysis, and problem area identification is diagnosis. In the research, data is essential. Methodologies used by researchers in various fields of study can differ. People who can concentrate solely on their goals in the mind are the ones that collect primary data. This ensures that the questions are pertinent to the goal. However, secondary data is not afforded this privilege of attention. And I am fully aware that the research paper's data must come from primary sources. However, as I already explained, everyone must adhere to the COVID guidelines in order to ensure their safety because it is convenient for COVID to go outside and collect the data. Since the information gathered was secondary, there were no such barriers. Even though this kind of work demands a lot of patience and time, I was quite inspired to do it.

4. Results

Secondary data were used in this article. Before it was finalised, a number of study papers were examined. This paper's technique is also incidental. We now face a problem with overfishing that requires an immediate fix. Fishing has been a way of life for people for thousands of years, and its effects are being felt now. As resources were depleted in tandem with rising catch rates, overfishing—characterized by production system inefficiency—became a common practise. The first overfishing incidents were documented in the 1800s when whale populations began to dwindle due to the demand for lamp oil made from their blubber. For human consumption, Atlantic cod and California sardines were gathered in the 1950s. Fishing is a traditional subsistence activity in caste-bound communities in India. Traditional coastal fishing communities have developed throughout the years, learning through hard work. The technology was only suitable for fishing as a meagre source of income. Up until its independence in 1972, India experienced this predicament. Fisheries seem to be at a standstill as demand for seafood grows along with worries about its effects. Overfishing is a problem that affects 85% of all fisheries worldwide. A rather homogenous aquatic ecozone is formed by the sea off the south-west coast of India, which includes the maritime states of Goa, Karnataka, and Kerala. There are 23,400 square kilometres of inshore or coastal waters in this area, with a maximum sustainable production of 700,00 tonnes (up to a depth of 50 metres).

These waterways have the highest potential for fishery productivity in India, with an average fishery productivity potential of 30 tonnes per square kilometre (or 300 kilos per hectare). (The total number of tonnes per square kilometre in India is 12.5). Only 12,570 square kilometres, or 4% of this coastal sea area with an estimated MSY of 400,000 tonnes, are contained inside Kerala State. The abundance of species reaching a variety of sizes at the age of maturity distinguishes the fishery resources in the tropical seas off Kerala state.

Each species is present in only a small number of locations throughout the coastal commons. According to estimates, at least 40% of the fish populations in the North East

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Atlantic and 87% of those in the Mediterranean and Black seas are currently being fished illegally in the European Union. Overfishing remains one of the biggest dangers to the health of marine ecosystems and has long-lasting effects on them. Numerous other markers of ocean health, such as biodiversity, food security, coastal livelihoods, and economics, are adversely affected by overfishing. Direct effects of overfishing include decreased fish biomass, which has an influence on biodiversity, fisheries sustainability, and marine environment damage from damaging fishing gear. According to recent assessments, between 40% and 70% of the fish stocks in Europe are currently unsustainable. Fish and ocean life are affected by climate change. Species, people, and ecosystems are already being impacted by climate change's effects on the marine environment.

Figure.11 Climate Change Impacts on marine ecosystems and goods and services provided to human society (Courtesy: chegg.com)

A summary of the ways that climate change may affect marine ecosystems and life is shown in Fig. 11. The physiological tolerance of marine species governs their responses to environmental change, and these organisms adjust their physiological function and behaviour in accordance with their evolutionary history. When temperature changes or ocean warming exceed an organism's ideal temperature range, physiological reactions are triggered that may have an impact on biological performance, including growth, reproduction, and survival. The timing of seasonal biological events is impacted by climate. Even though there have been some accomplishments in reducing overfishing, efforts to decrease the world's fishing capacity have so far been ineffective, with the exception of a modest decrease inside select industrialised nations. Assuring global food security while limiting fishing-related changes to the composition and operation of the marine ecosystem is the primary objective. Redistributing fishing pressure to a wider range of ecosystem elements through balanced harvesting is an obvious option. The idea is to spread out moderate fishing pressure in proportion to each ecosystem component's inherent productivity. This calls for an ecosystem-level selection pattern that differs from the one used today in the majority of global fisheries. This suggests that there should be a

spatial balance in exploitation. Furthermore, while relative fishing mortality may have been excessively high for some for-age species, the suggested strategy is equally applicable to species at low trophic levels. Reducing or temporarily stopping direct targeted fishing mortality and just permitting allowable incidental catch could speed the recovery of overfished stocks.

5. Conclusions

“Excess of everything is bad” a very common proverb fits perfectly in the topic of Overfishing. Fishing is good but in a sustainable way. Though there have been so many research papers on overfishing , I tried to explain the negative impacts of overfishing, causes of overfishing , and a short list including the fishes who are in the list of endangered and extinction. Overfishing has occurred not only due to intensive and selective fishing but also because of commercial fishing. Large businesses are searching for enormous profits. While smaller fish and species with lower economic importance have altered less, or even grown, the biomass of giant fish top predators and highly valued species has significantly decreased. The biggest issue with outright outlawing overfishing is the fishermen who, due to a lack of alternative economic options, are more or less dependent on it. Although a capitalist can simply leave the fishing industry, the future of the fishermen is dependent on the sea and its shared resources.

Figure.12 The Ancient Tradition of Stilt fishing in Galle, Sri Lanka (Courtesy: artphotolimited.com)

Figure.13 The Ancient Tradition of Stilt fishing in Galle, Sri Lanka (Courtesy: wpengine.com)

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Additionally, fisheries management and popular management techniques such (TAC Total Allowable Catch) In certain regions, such as those depicted in Figs. 12 and 13, fishing is not only a primary occupation but also an important component of tradition and custom. So, while we can't fully cease fishing, we can do it sustainably. Fish workers and endangered fish can only be saved by sustainable fishing. A balanced overfishing condition can be maintained by fishing more than the stock can generate. Limiting fishing effort is another way to create sustainable fisheries. In order to stop overfishing and increase fish catch at the same time, a balanced harvest strategy is preferred. Instead of providing an exact goal, balanced fishing harvesting gives fishery management a direction. Fisheries managers, fishermen, and scientists that have mostly focused on a single species or small group of species have largely solved the overfishing problem up to this point. Instead of focusing on sustainable fishing, it is simpler to say. Sustainable fishing is not an easy goal to achieve. Before achieving the goal of reducing the number of catchers and implementing new fishing techniques to enable fish stocks to recover, there are a number of difficulties that must be taken into consideration. Scientists and NGOs are at odds with industry. NGOs developed shame campaigns and blamed industries for contributing to the extinction of certain species as shown in Fig.14.

Figure.14 NGOs developed shame campaigns and blamed industries for contributing to the extinction of certain species(Courtesy: radicalphilosophy.com)

NGOs, Scientists and industry from retailers to catchers have to work together. Stop buying or selling fish to improve fishery will not work neither blaming or shame campaigns.

These methods can be trying to improve fishery

- Healthy fish stocks.
- Protection of habitats and marine life.
- Effective management of fishing activities.

But the question is will stakeholders take risk??

Will regulators follow scientific advice??

Only with considerably more varied participation from the education sector, government officials, scientists, environmental organizations, the media, food producers, and consumers can the suggested approach be practical. By developing harvest models that take into account the marine ecology, science and technology can contribute.

5. References

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